
PROSPECTS FOR IMPROVING FINANCIAL SUPPORT FOR INVESTMENT ACTIVITIES IN THE CONTEXT OF GLOBALIZATION

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Abstract: In this article, the sources of investment funds and specific features of financial sources are discussed and given overall conclusions with current scientific analyses.

Key words: investment, innovation, gross domestic product, investor, investment activity, investment financing.

The high probability of unfavorable development of investment enterprises in our country through financial support of investment activities in the context of globalization requires expanding sources of financial resources. It is necessary to evaluate investment projects and consider investment flows in general, taking into account modern trends caused by various negative factors. Regarding the first, it should be noted that although assessing the quality of investment projects is problematic, it is important to bring the assessment results to a reasonable level.

During 2020, 18 loans worth \$ 3.1 billion were provided to the Republic of Uzbekistan by international financial institutions, including the World Bank, the Asian Development Bank, the French Development Agency, the Saudi Development Fund, the Chinese Exim Bank, the Korean Exim Bank, and financial organizations of Japan, and the Republic of Uzbekistan entered the top five countries in Europe and Central Asia in terms of the volume of its project portfolio in the World Bank system. This indicates that international financial institutions have high confidence in the reforms being implemented intensively in our country.

Attracting investment is a priority in the development of any country. In this regard, it is appropriate to recall the opinion expressed by our Honorable President in his Address of December 29, 2020.

In this regard, it is no exaggeration to say that we have fully achieved our priority tasks set for this year, no matter how difficult it may be, based on the ideas put forward by our President, namely, “we must learn to live and work in the conditions of a pandemic.” In this regard, it is important to attract investments in our country to sustainably develop sectors of our economy.

Table 1

Issuer Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan on behalf of the Republic of Uzbekistan	Issuer Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan on behalf of the Republic of Uzbekistan	
Rating level BB-	Rating level BB-	
Global coordinator JP Morgan Chase	Global coordinator JP Morgan Chase	
Bookrunner agents Citigroup, Gazprombank, JP Morgan	Bookrunner agents Citigroup, Gazprombank, JP Morgan	
Maturity February 20, 2024	Maturity February 20, 2024	Maturity February 20, 2024
(5-year) February 20, 2029	(5-year) February 20, 2029	(5-year) February 20, 2029
(10-year)	(10-year)	(10-year)
Value of issued securities 500 million US dollars 500 million US dollars	Value of issued securities 500 million US dollars 500 million US dollars	Value of issued securities 500 million US dollars 500 million US dollars
Coupon rate 4.750% 5.375%	Coupon rate 4.750% 5.375%	Coupon rate 4.750% 5.375%
Benchmark spread +222 bps +266.4 bps	Benchmark spread +222 bps +266.4 bps	Benchmark spread +222 bps

		+266.4 bps
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The results of the above analysis show that it is necessary to expand the financing of investment activities in our republic by introducing public sales of shares of large enterprises to local and foreign investors in open markets in a syndicated manner with international “bookrunner” companies.

On December 28, 2020, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-4937 “On measures to implement the Investment Program of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2021-2023” was adopted.

Based on this resolution, the parameters of the development of capital investments carried out by the Ministry of Finance in the field of financial support of investment activities in our country can be seen in the table below.

Analyzing the table data, the share of budget funds in the structure of centralized investment expenditures is planned to be 17,700 billion soums in 2021, while this figure will increase to 19,650 billion soums by 2022. it is planned that it will amount to soum. It can be seen from the data of this table that in 2023, compared to 2022, the budget expenses will increase by 1.12 times.

Conclusions

Thus, the internal and external sources of financial support for investment activities at the macro-economic and micro-economic levels are fundamentally different from each other. The need to clarify the classification (classification) of the sources of financing investment activity depends on the objective changes in the transition to the market model of investment, the distribution of functions of the state and enterprises in the investment process, the investment market, as well as the development of the system of institutions whose main task is to collect investments and then deploy them in business activities. The analysis of sources of financial support for investments in countries with a developed market economy shows that the share of internal resources in the volume of total investment costs differs significantly in different countries depending on many objective and subjective factors. In the economic literature, the ratio between internal and external sources of investment in Western countries is estimated differently.

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